

Mobility of Ions on Paper as a Function of Electrolyte Concentration

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Ionophoretic mobilities of Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , Co^{+2} and Zn^{+2} ions on paper have been measured and corrected for electroosmotic and tortuosity effects at different concentrations of hydrochloric acid as supporting electrolyte. They decrease due perhaps to complex formation with increase in the concentration of the acid. The corrected mobilities are of the same order as those in free solution.

The factors governing the migration of any ion in solution in an electric field are well known¹. The speed of ions can be accurately measured with good reproducibility if optimum conditions are worked out. In addition, corrections have to be applied for (i) electroosmotic and (ii) tortuosity factor or 'added migration path length' owing to the winding nature of the path in filter paper.

These two corrections have been discussed earlier² following the treatment by McDonald and coworkers³. The latter have shown that acceptable values of mobility of small as well as macroions may be obtained after making these two corrections.

EXPERIMENTAL

In this communication we have determined the ionophoretic mobilities of Cu^{+2} , Ni^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , Co^{+2} and Zn^{+2} ions on paper at different concentrations of HCl as the supporting medium. Corrections for electroosmotic and tortuosity effects have been applied to get the true values.

As mentioned earlier², four measurements were made for each set of experimental conditions. These included measurement of ionographic mobility and R_D , a modified R_T as in classical chromatography, of the migrant and of the electroosmotic indicator.

The general expression is:

$$U = \frac{U_m}{R_D^m} \pm \frac{U_{el}}{R_D^{el}}$$

U_m denotes the ionographic mobility of the migrant and U_{el} that of the indicator; R_D^m and R_D^{el} denote the R_D values of the migrant and the indicator, respectively. This expression has been used to calculate free solution mobilities of some inorganic ions at low

1. R. J. Block, E. L. Durrum and G. Zweig, "A Manual of Paper Chromatography and Paper Electrophoresis", New York, 1958.
2. M. M. Lahiri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 42, 843.
3. H. J. McDonald and E. W. Beams, Jr., *J. Chromatog.*, 1960, 4, 34.

pH. The negative sign is used for positively charged migrant and the positive sign for negatively charged species. The necessary details of the instrument and its operation were discussed earlier¹.

A series of similar experiments were performed with the ions mentioned with HCl adjusted to pH values 0.69, 1.0, 1.3, 2.0 and 2.3. The measured distances of migration of the ions and of glucose are shown in Table I. The corresponding R_D values are given in Table II. Table III shows the observed mobilities of the ions and their computed free solution mobilities. Their variations with molarity of HCl are presented graphically in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Potential gradient = 3.508 volts/cm; time = 30 minutes; temp. = 24-26°.
 Electrolytic medium = Hydrochloric acid.

Migrant	Distance of migration (mm.) in:				
	0.005 M HCl	0.01M HCl	0.05 M HCl	0.1 M HCl	0.2 M HCl
Glucose	0.00	2.0	2.5	2.5	2.5
Cu ⁺⁺	8.5	12.5	15.0	14.0	13.0
Ni ⁺⁺	10.4	15.5	16.5	15.5	13.5
Fe ⁺⁺	2.5	6.5	12.0	10.2	8.9
Co ⁺⁺	10.0	13.9	16.0	14.0	13.0
Zn ⁺⁺	10.5	13.3	17.0	14.8	13.0

TABLE II

Determination of R_D values in hydrochloric acid of different concentrations

Substances	0.005 M HCl	0.01 M HCl	0.05M HCl	0.1 M HCl	0.2 M HCl
Glucose	0.91	0.96	0.97	0.91	0.94
Cu ⁺⁺	0.34	0.56	1.00	0.94	0.98
Ni ⁺⁺	0.35	0.63	1.00	0.94	0.97
Fe ⁺⁺	0.94	0.94	1.00	0.94	0.98
Co ⁺⁺	0.35	0.58	1.00	0.94	0.97
Zn ⁺⁺	0.40	0.56	1.00	0.94	0.96

TABLE III

Variation of mobility of ions with HCl concentration

Migrant	0.005 M		0.01 M		0.05 M		0.1 M		0.2 M		Extra- polated value of mobility $\times 10^4$ (cm. ² /v-sec.)
	Observed	Computed									
Glucose	0.00	—	0.33	—	0.41	—	0.43	—	0.42	—	—
Cu ⁺⁺	3.95	3.95	3.53	3.20	2.37	1.96	2.35	1.92	2.10	1.68	2.10
Ni ⁺⁺	4.70	4.70	3.90	3.57	2.93	2.52	2.61	2.18	2.20	1.78	2.80
Fe ⁺⁺	0.42	0.42	1.09	0.76	1.90	1.49	1.71	1.28	1.45	1.03	1.65
Co ⁺⁺	4.52	4.52	3.63	3.30	2.53	2.12	2.35	1.92	2.12	1.70	2.25
Zn ⁺⁺	4.10	4.10	3.76	3.43	2.69	2.28	2.49	2.06	2.14	1.72	2.45

Fig. 1 shows that except Fe^{3+} , mobilities of all the ions studied fall sharply up to about 0.02 M HCl and then gradually the acid concentration is increased beyond this

FIG. 1

molarity up to 0.2M. In case of Fe^{3+} ion, the mobility sharply increases, attains a maximum value at about 0.02M and then decreases slowly as in the case of other ions. Hydrolysis of Fe^{3+} ion at lower acid concentration probably causes lowering of mobility. The decrease in mobility at higher strength of hydrochloric acid (above 0.05M) for all the ions may be caused by complex formation. These observations suggest that for a more accurate estimate of mobility, the electrolyte concentrations should be suitably adjusted. The abnormally high values of mobility of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Zn^{2+} in the more dilute acid concentrations may be due to an overestimate of the tortuosity correction and no correction whatsoever for the electroosmotic effect as a result of the immobility of glucose at such low acid concentration. The mobility at zero acid concentration corresponds to a condition where the ions are really free, in the sense that the retarding effect of the electrolyte or complex formation, whatever be the case, is eliminated. The values so extrapolated which are slightly higher than those at moderate concentrations of the electrolyte are given in the last column of Table III. The extrapolation has been advisedly done with the linear portion of the curves beyond 0.01M, because of the uncertainties, mentioned above, involved in the region of low acid concentration. The extrapolated values compare favourably with those in solution for some of the known ionic species.

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